

On Mobile Positioning Via Cellular Synchronization Assisted Refinement (CeSAR) in LTE and GSM Networks

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Abstract—Inferring user equipment (UE) location in cellular networks via uplink timing management presents attractive possibilities in an increasingly mobile-connected world. Power constrained mobile devices with ever more common applications that rely on location-based services demand an alternate solution to positioning than a Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) and its derivatives. In this paper we provide analysis of mobile positioning via timing advance (TA), an LTE parameter also accounted for in legacy network deployments. Specifically, we provide analysis for a TA-based method Cellular Synchronization Assisted Refinement (CeSAR). We demonstrate through analysis and simulation how CeSAR can increase accuracy in timing advance-based positioning by several hundreds of meters with no impact to radio link level traffic. CeSAR is shown to be robust to situations where unassisted TA-based positioning can provide poor positioning accuracy.

Index Terms—positioning, geolocation, timing advance, Weibull distribution, LTE, GSM

I. INTRODUCTION

The role of mobile devices in everyday life is becoming more prominent everyday. Just between 2014 and 2015 the number of Long Term Evolution (LTE) subscribers increased from 252.5 million to 634.9 million worldwide, an increase of 151% [1]. With the advent of the internet of things and increasing world population the number of connected devices will only continue to rise. Additionally, mobile applications increasingly rely on location awareness in order to provide a quality of service today's user requires.

Modern solutions to imbuing a mobile device with location awareness rely heavily on a global navigation satellite system such as the Global Positioning System (GPS), assisted-GPS, or other alternatives such as the European Union's Galileo. Besides requiring extra hardware to take advantage of these systems [2], satellite-based solutions are also not power frugal [3]. The latter weakness has been significant enough to warrant serious research into designing protocols around an awareness of battery limitations [4], [5].

Other solutions to location awareness such as observed time difference of arrival and enhanced cell-ID (E-CID) are currently supported in the LTE standard [6], but add to network traffic via signaling to and from an enhanced serving mobility location center and add to the overall complexity of the standard.

A historically overlooked existing network parameter that can aid in mobile positioning is the timing advance (TA). Introduced with the Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM) in the early 1990s, the timing advance aided the user equipment (UE) in synchronizing to a serving base station utilizing time division duplexing access schemes. Early work recognized the potential of using the TA to localize a UE, but never achieved widespread acclaim, perhaps due to poor performance in early networks as early technologies did not require tight synchronization [7]. However, with the inauguration of LTE, and consumer demand for ever increasing data rates, tighter synchronization was needed and the TA resolution has since improved [8].

In this paper we intend to reinvigorate research into the TA as a useful parameter in mobile positioning due to its elegance as a solution, its increased resolution in the LTE standard, zero additional power requirement, and because it can be utilized with negligible network traffic overhead. This work will show the usefulness of the TA first through analysis and then validate our findings in simulation. We will build the analytic case for TA via a technique previously introduced, Cellular Synchronization Assisted Refinement (CeSAR) [9], which can dramatically improve the performance of TA-based positioning without adding any other requirement on UE power or hardware, or on network capabilities. In fact, the only requirement from CeSAR is that a single passive sensor is added to the physical area a base station serves.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. A stochastic analysis of TA as a positioning aid along with implications and insights are presented in Section II. We continue our analysis in Section III by evaluating the theoretical

Fig. 1. The timing advance annulus is shown around an eNB. A positioning estimate along with a notional UE location is represented.

performance of CeSAR after a brief overview of the method. The analytical results presented in the preceding sections are illustrated and supported with simulated results in Section IV. Finally, our conclusions are presented in Section V.

II. LOCATION INFORMATION INFERENCE VIA TIMING ADVANCE

It has long been known that the timing advance parameter in cellular networks could be used in locating a subscriber [7]. In this section we will provide analysis to show exactly how much location-based information can be gleaned in an LTE timing advance parameter assuming the UE is connected to only one base station, termed enhanced Node B (eNB) in the LTE standard, and has no secondary carriers configured.

An important assumption we make throughout our analysis in the remainder of this paper is that measurement error is negligible and that the channel is strictly line-of-sight. We assume this position in order to allow for a tractable exposition that highlights the novelty of positioning via a TA. Therefore a limitation of this work is that it is, strictly speaking, only applicable to an environment where high precision measurements are possible and there is no multipath propagation. However, our results are a necessary first step into this type of positioning analysis and provide a jumping off point from which future research can investigate the effect of different types of error.

Throughout this section we assume that the closer a UE is to the eNB, the more likely it is connected to that eNB. Therefore it is also more likely that the UE will be closer to the eNB than distal to it. To this end, let the UE be located at position $\chi = (P, \Theta)$ (in polar coordinates) where $P \sim U[0, c]$ and $\Theta \sim U[0, 2\pi)$, where c is the maximum radius of the cell,

$U[a, b]$ is the uniform distribution with support $\in [a, b]$, and Θ is given in radians.

We assume that a passive listener, or sensor, observes a timing advance parameter and can link that parameter to a specific UE of interest¹. We illustrate in Figure 1 how with this information the listener knows that the UE is located within an annulus of width w_{TA} meters [10]. Once the sensor has ascertained in which annulus the UE is located the sensor is then left to estimate the UE location, $\hat{\chi}$, randomly within that annulus. The error can be described by the well known formula

$$\epsilon = \sqrt{\rho^2 + \hat{\rho}^2 + \rho\hat{\rho}\cos(\theta - \hat{\theta})} \quad (1)$$

where ϵ is the error in meters, ρ is actual UE radius, $\hat{\rho}$ is the estimated UE radius, θ is the actual UE angle, and $\hat{\theta}$ is the estimated UE angle. Without loss of generality we may set $\theta = 0$. By virtue of the observed annulus we may also restrict $|\rho - \hat{\rho}| \leq w_{TA}$.

Lemma 1: *Let all neighboring eNBs be the same distance from the connected eNB, then the resulting annuli will be distributed according to the following*

$$f_P(\rho) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \delta(\rho - w_{TA}/2 + nw_{TA}), \quad (2)$$

where $\delta(\cdot)$ is the Dirac delta function and $N = \lceil c/w_{TA} \rceil$.

To show Lemma 1, we perform a trivial transformation of coordinates such that the connected eNB is located at the origin. Keeping the structure of $\hat{\chi}$ in mind, it is easy to see that the distance of the UE from the eNB is distributed by $U[0, c]$. The probability that the UE is located in the n th annulus is $\int_n 1/c d\rho = 1/N$.

In order to show the effect of timing advance resolution on location inference we begin by considering the case where $w_{TA} \rightarrow 0$.

Lemma 2: *The limit of the distribution of annuli from the connected eNB converges to a uniform random variable as the width of the annulus approaches zero.*

$$\lim_{w_{TA} \rightarrow 0} f_P(\rho) = U[0, c] \quad (3)$$

Consider the cumulative density of (2)

$$F_P(\rho) = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \frac{i+1}{N} I_{[\gamma_1, \gamma_2]}(\rho) \quad (4)$$

where $I_{[\gamma_1, \gamma_2]}(\cdot)$ is the indicator function with support $\in [iw_{TA} + w_{TA}/2, (i+1)w_{TA} + w_{TA}/2)$. The stepwise interval decreases as $w_{TA} \rightarrow 0$ resulting in

$$\lim_{w_{TA} \rightarrow 0} F_P(\rho) = \frac{1}{c}\rho. \quad (5)$$

Applying the definition of a probability density function, we can then take the derivative of (5) to arrive at (3).

Corollary 1: *As $w_{TA} \rightarrow 0$, $\hat{r} \rightarrow r$.*

¹We note that this task would be non-trivial for several reasons. The interested reader is directed to [9] for further information on the practicalities associated with this assumption.

Fig. 2. The density of errors is shown for the case described by a scaled (12) denoted by \circ and (7) denoted by $+$.

Recall the definition of (1) with restriction $|r - \hat{r}| \leq w_{TA}$. The corollary easily follows and suggests that the error imposed by the random distribution of radii within an annulus vanishes to zero as the resolution of the timing advance increases. Thus, in this theoretical framework, by observation of a timing advance a listener has perfect knowledge of the distance of the UE from the origin. The discussion in Section IV will elaborate on the significance of this observation.

Because of Corollary 1, and by arbitrarily setting $\theta = 0$ we may simplify (1) to

$$\epsilon = 2P|\sin(\hat{\theta}/2)| \quad (6)$$

where $|\cdot|$ denotes the modulus operator. Further, by symmetry, we may restrict $\hat{\Theta} \sim U[0, \pi]$.

Theorem 1: *The density of distribution of errors given through observation of a timing advance is approximated by*

$$f_E(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{\pi c} \left[\log \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{\epsilon^2}{4c^2}} + 1 \right) - \log \left(\frac{\epsilon}{2c} \right) \right] I_{[0, 2c]}(\epsilon) \quad (7)$$

where $\log(\cdot)$ denotes the natural logarithm.

First, consider the transform

$$\Lambda = \frac{\Theta}{2}. \quad (8)$$

This yields the intermediate equation

$$E = 2P|\sin(\Lambda)| \quad (9)$$

where

$$\Lambda \sim U[0, \pi/2]. \quad (10)$$

Next since Λ spans only $[0, \pi/2]$ we may drop the modulus and apply the transform

$$Y = \sin(\Lambda) \quad (11)$$

Fig. 3. The timing advance annulus is shown around an eNB alongside a sensor performing CeSAR refinement. The UE locus which is the intersection of the CeSAR ring and the timing advance annulus, in this case, is disjoint.

where

$$p_Y(y) = \frac{2}{\pi\sqrt{1-y^2}} I_{[0,1]}(y). \quad (12)$$

The remaining transformation

$$E = 2PY \quad (13)$$

can be applied via convolution to obtain the final density in (7).

Corollary 2: *Minimum location information inference via timing advance is described by the edges of a first order Voronoi diagram defined by the eNB locations.*

To illustrate this corollary, consider (12) scaled to a certain distance c and (7) shown in Figure 2. The intermediate transform, (12), can be understood as the density of error given the UE remains at a fixed distance from the eNB. Similarly, the final transform, (7), can be understood as the density of error given the UE's distance to the eNB is changing. In (12) the density is skewed towards larger error near the asymptote (i.e., negative skew). Conversely, the density in (7) is skewed towards smaller errors (i.e., positive skew) due to the product of random variables and subsequent convolution of densities. Therefore, a listener's ability to infer location by timing advance only is minimized if the UE maintains lines whose points are equidistant to the nearest two eNBs (hence the Voronoi diagram).

III. LOCATION INFORMATION INFERENCE VIA CESAR

We now turn our attention to the CeSAR method of location information inference.

A. Overview of CeSAR

CeSAR is an entirely passive method in which a local sensor can refine a UE locus inferred by timing advance observation. CeSAR involves the listener using downlink

synchronization to refine an area within the initial TA annulus where the UE may be located. First the sensor establishes downlink synchronization with the network by observing the eNB primary and secondary search signal. Once the sensor has synchronized to the network, it then estimates the downlink frame timing at the eNB by calculating the propagation delay between it and the local eNB. It should be noted that downlink synchronization can be achieved entirely passively without initiating the random access procedure, thus the sensor does not contribute to network traffic. Next the sensor listens for TAs sent from the eNB to the UE. With this knowledge the sensor knows exactly when the UE will transmit its uplink frames. Finally, because the sensor is synchronized to the serving eNB it can calculate the propagation time from the UE to the sensor thus creating a circle of negligible width² around the sensor on which the UE is located. A general scenario describing the operation of CeSAR is provided in Figure 3. Two special cases of a realization of CeSAR are presented in Figure 4 which will be discussed by Definition 1.

B. Theoretical performance of CeSAR

The analysis of CeSAR begins with the conditional assumption that the magnitude of the angle describing the arc-locus (given as θ_1 in Figure 4) on which the UE lies follows a Weibull distribution

$$f_{\Theta}(\theta) = \frac{k}{\beta} \left(\frac{\theta}{\beta}\right)^{k-1} e^{-(\theta/\beta)^k} \quad (14)$$

where k is a shape parameter and β is a scale parameter.

This assumption is supported by a multiplicity of application in the literature. To only name a few applications, the Weibull distribution has been used to provide a more robust description of fading channels [11], model wind turbine generator capacity [12], and to assess dielectric breakdown voltage [13]. This model has also received wide acclaim in reliability engineering (e.g., [14], [15]). The Weibull distribution has achieved such wide acclaim due in large part in its ability to interpolate between an exponential distribution when $k = 1$ to a Rayleigh distribution when $k = 2$ to mimicking a Gaussian distribution when $k = 3.5$. The Weibull model is then a natural starting point, able to describe a random variable which results from processes with varying levels of randomness and correlation.

Second, to support our case for the Weibull distribution, is its ability to accurately model behavior with little available data. In these situations the Weibull distribution's shape parameter k is assumed to be known and thus reduces to a one parameter model allowing for use with small datasets. This will be a valuable property in application.

With this antecedant in mind we proceed to derive the probability distribution of error to be expected with CeSAR.

Definition 1: For all possible cases involving CeSAR localization there are two classes of loci. The first (class 1) is a contiguous set and the second (class 2) is non-contiguous set.

²For the sake of a simple exposition we neglect the effects of multi-path propagation and shadowing although consideration of these factors is a natural extension of this work.

Fig. 4. The class 1 and class 2 cases where the arc-locus is contiguous and non-contiguous respectively is presented. The angle describing the arc-locus is denoted by θ_1 . The angle describing the separation of subsets of an arc-locus, in the case of a class 2 locus, is denoted by θ_2 .

Definition 1 is presented graphically in Figure 4. Due to the nature of CeSAR, it follows that the arc-locus will always be some non-empty set. The class 1 loci involve cases where the locus is not split by the inner ring of the TA annulus; the class 2 loci involve the converse.

Lemma 3: Given the angles describing the arc-loci derived by CeSAR are distributed according to the Weibull model, the probability of error in class 1 loci is

$$f_{E,1}(\epsilon) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathcal{J}_i \mathcal{W}_\pi(k, \alpha_{i,1}) I_{[0, 2P_i]}(\epsilon) \quad (15)$$

such that

$$P_N = c \quad (16)$$

where $\alpha = 2 \arcsin(\epsilon/2P_i)/\beta_1$, $\mathcal{W}_\pi(\cdot)$ denotes a Weibull distribution truncated to π and appropriately scaled, and \mathcal{J}_i denotes the jacobian of the transformation.

Let $\Theta_1 \sim \mathcal{W}_\pi(k, \beta_1)$. We then adapt (6) to

$$E_i = 2P_i |\sin(\Theta_1/2)| \quad (17)$$

where P_i is a scalar quantity and $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$. Beginning with the sub-transform

$$\Lambda = \Theta_1/2 \quad (18)$$

we arrive at

$$f_\Lambda(\lambda) = 2\mathcal{W}_\pi(\beta_1/2, k)I_{[0, \pi/2]}(\lambda). \quad (19)$$

Next the transform

$$Y = |\sin(\Lambda)| \quad (20)$$

is applied, where again due to the support of Λ we may drop the modulus yielding

$$f_Y(y) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{1-y^2}}\mathcal{W}_\pi(k, \beta_1/2 \arcsin(y))I_{[0,1]}(y). \quad (21)$$

The final sub-transform $E = 2P_i Y$ is then applied where P_i is a constant to yield

$$f_E(\epsilon) = \frac{2}{P_i \sqrt{1 - (\epsilon/2P_i)^2}}\mathcal{W}_\pi(k, \alpha_{i,1})I_{[0,2P_i]}(y) \quad (22)$$

where $\alpha_{i,1} = \beta_1/2 \arcsin(\epsilon/2P_i)$. We may further simplify (22), by setting $\mathcal{J}_i = 2/P_i \sqrt{1 - (\epsilon/2P_i)^2}$. We consider the case where there are N possible radii each P_i in magnitude. In keeping with the assumption that the UE's distance from the eNB is uniformly distributed we let each P_i be equal in probability, thus

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathcal{J}_i \mathcal{W}_\pi(k, \alpha_{i,1}) I_{[0,2P_i]}(\epsilon). \quad (23)$$

Finally, we invoke the result in Lemma 2 to justify the use of the limit in defining $f_{E,1}(\epsilon)$ arriving at (15). Note here that we have formulated the randomness in the radius in this manner in order to avoid a convolution of densities that has no closed form solution.

Note that (16) implies the radius of the CeSAR circle varies uniformly $\in [0, c]$ despite the theoretical scenario where the sensor may be on one side of the cell and the UE on the other side. The radius of the CeSAR ring should then vary $\in [0, 2c]$. However, this will be true only in the case where the correlation between P and Θ is non-zero, otherwise the transformation in (17) may result in errors which are larger than the cell size. Therefore, in order to realize meaningful results we approximate $P \sim U[0, c]$ and P and Θ as uncorrelated.

Lemma 4: *Given the angles describing the arc-loci derived by CeSAR are distributed according to the Weibull model, the probability of error in class 2 loci when the position estimate is chosen in the correct contiguous set of the two in the locus is*

$$f_{E,2}^\dagger(\epsilon) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathcal{J}_i \mathcal{W}_\pi(k, \alpha_{i,2}, \nu) I_{[2P_i \sin(\nu), 2P_i]}(\epsilon) \quad (24)$$

where ν is some offset parameter corresponding to a minimum angular separation thus making $\mathcal{W}(\cdot)$ a the three parameter Weibull distribution,

CeSAR will always choose the position estimate to be the closest to the center of the locus in order to minimize the largest overall error. However, in the case of class 2 loci, there are two points that are equidistant to the center of the locus and thus CeSAR will randomly choose between the two. This lemma applies to the case where the position estimate is in the same contiguous set as the UE.

The three parameter Weibull distribution adds a translation term in order to move the overall distribution from it's default support of $[0, \infty)$ to $[\nu, \infty)$. Therefore the justification of Lemma 3 applies until the application of the transform

$$Y = \sin(\Lambda). \quad (25)$$

Because the $\arcsin(\cdot)$ function is only defined $\in [-\pi/2, \pi/2]$ we must include a second transform in terms of $\arccos(\cdot)$ to account for that portion of the density shifted by ν . However, in practice we find this aliasing to be negligible and thus omit it from our derivation for the sake of simplicity. With that difference aside, we may apply the remaining justification of Lemma 3 to arrive at (24).

Lemma 5: *Given the angles describing the arc-loci derived by CeSAR are distributed according to the Weibull model and the angles describing the separation of non-contiguous loci are $\sim U[0, \pi)$, the probability of error in class 2 loci where the position estimate is not in the same contiguous set as the UE is*

$$f_{E,2}^\ddagger(\epsilon) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathcal{J}_i \Xi_i I_{[0,2P_i]}(\epsilon). \quad (26)$$

where

$$\Xi_i = 1 - e^{-(\alpha_{i,2} + \nu/\beta_2)^k} + e^{-(\alpha_{i,2}^\ddagger + \nu/\beta_2)^k} - e^{-(\pi/2)^k} \quad (27)$$

and $\alpha_{i,2}^\ddagger = 2 \arccos(\epsilon/2P_i)/\beta_2$

Here we begin by assuming the random variable input to (6) is $\Theta = \mathcal{W}_\pi(k, \alpha_{i,2}, \nu) + U[0, \pi)$. Thus this overall distribution of angles is the convolution of densities resulting in

$$f_\Theta(\theta) = \frac{1}{\pi} \left(1 - e^{-(\frac{\theta-\nu}{\beta_2})^k} \right) I_{[\nu, \pi+\nu]}(\theta) + \frac{1}{\pi} \left(e^{-(\frac{\theta-\pi-\nu}{\beta_2})^k} - e^{-(\frac{\pi}{\beta_2})^k} \right) I_{[\pi+\nu, 2\pi+\nu]}(\theta). \quad (28)$$

The input density is then transformed as in the justification for Lemmas 3 and 4. As in Lemma 4, consideration must be given to the support of the transform $Y = |\sin(\Lambda)|$ such that after applying this transform the resulting density of Y is

$$f_Y(y) = J \left[1 - e^{-(\frac{2 \arcsin(y)-\nu}{\beta_2})^k} \right] I_{[\sin(\nu/2), 1]}(y) + J \left[1 - e^{-(\frac{2 \arccos(y)+\pi/2-\nu}{\beta_2})^k} \right] I_{[\cos(\nu/2), 1]}(y) + J \left[e^{-(\frac{2 \arccos(y)+\pi/2-\nu}{\beta_2})^k} - e^{-(\frac{\pi}{\beta_2})^k} \right] I_{[\cos(\nu/2), 1]}(y) \quad (29)$$

where J is the intermediate jacobian $2/\pi \sqrt{1-y^2}$. Strictly speaking a fourth term would also be necessary to accommodate the support of $\Lambda \in [\nu, 2\pi + \nu]$ for that portion of $\Lambda \in [2\pi, 2\pi + \nu]$; however it is omitted here for clarity as

Fig. 5. The density of CeSAR errors is shown for the case described by a single summand in (31) denoted by \circ and the entire sum of (31) denoted by $+$.

it has a negligible contribution to (29). The crux of Lemma 5, behind us we follow the progression of Lemmas 3 and 4 to their termini realizing (26).

Lemma 6: *The distribution of errors in class 2 loci are described by*

$$f_{E,2}(\epsilon) = \zeta f_{E,2}^{\dagger}(\epsilon) + (1 - \zeta) f_{E,2}^{\ddagger}(\epsilon). \quad (30)$$

where ω is the probability that the position estimate is in the same contiguous set as the UE.

By the law of noncontradiction the position estimate cannot be in the same contiguous set as the UE and simultaneously also not in the same contiguous set. It follows that in a class 2 realization of CeSAR the error distribution must be distributed by either (24) via Lemma 4 with probability ω or (26) via Lemma 5 with probability $(1 - \omega)$.

Theorem 2: *The distribution of errors in any given realization of CeSAR is described by*

$$f_E(\epsilon) = \eta f_{E,1}(\epsilon) + (1 - \eta) f_{E,2}(\epsilon) \quad (31)$$

where η is the probability that the locus is contiguous.

Also by the law of noncontradiction, the locus cannot be simultaneously split and contiguous. It follows that the locus will be contiguous with probability η and split with probability $(1 - \eta)$. By Lemma 3, if the locus is continuous the distribution of errors will follow $f_{E,1}(\epsilon)$. By Lemma 6, if the locus is non-contiguous the distribution of errors will follow $f_{E,2}(\epsilon)$.

Corollary 3: *CeSAR is robust to minimum location information inference when the UE follows the edges of a first order Voronoi diagram defined by the eNB locations.*

Different from the corollary drawn in Section II, the difference in information inference in CeSAR between a UE changing its distance to a eNB and a UE maintaining the edges of the Voronoi cell described by the eNB deployment is less severe. Consider a single summand in (31) where we

Fig. 6. The positioning error using timing advance inference only is presented. The simulated error in LTE and GSM networks is presented alongside the theoretical prediction.

set $i = N$ to represent the extreme case where the UE is at the cell boundary. This term represents the distribution of error predicted by CeSAR given the UE maintains the cell boundary. This distribution along with the entire sum described by (31) is presented in Figure 5. The skewness of the fixed distance distribution is positive as is the skewness of the entirety (31). This suggests that CeSAR will not realize drastically different performance when a UE maintains constant distance from the serving eNB (conf. Corollary 2).

IV. RESULTS

In this section we present our analysis alongside data obtained through Monte Carlo simulation. The simulation is designed to mimic a single modern eNB cell with a radius of approximately 500 meters. Each simulation is independent and can be thought of a IID realization of E derived in Sections II or III. For each simulation we consider it equally likely that a locus will be non-contiguous or that it will be contiguous ($\eta = 0.5$). Given that a locus is non-contiguous, we consider it equally likely that CeSAR will choose the position estimate to lie in the correct contiguous subset of the locus as it is to choose the wrong subset ($\omega = 0.5$).

A. Unassisted Timing Advance Inference

First, we consider the case where the sensor does not use CeSAR, but only infers location by observation of the timing advance parameter. The theoretical performance is shown next to simulated results in Figure 6. The most immediately recognizable result here is the difference in performance in LTE and GSM networks³. Therefore Figure 6 provides insight into the effect of TA resolution on location inference. Notably, less resolution (e.g., GSM) provides less small errors but also

³A GSM network specifies the timing advance resolution as 554 meters [7] and a LTE network specifies the timing advance resolution as 78.125 meters [10].

Fig. 7. The positioning error using CeSAR is presented. The error simulated in an LTE network is presented alongside the theoretical prediction. Additionally, the theoretical performance of the unassisted case is presented for comparison.

Fig. 8. The positioning error when a UE maintains constant range from the eNB is presented with both the unassisted and CeSAR assisted methods. In case presented, the UE maintains the cell edge.

less larger errors, the converse of is true for better resolution in the uplink synchronization (e.g., LTE).

The second result illustrated in Figure 6 is that the theoretical performance describes networks that provide high uplink resolution well. Recall the transformation (6) used to derive the theoretical performance. Here, P is given as a uniform random variable on $[0, c]$ which corresponds to the case where the TA resolution is exact. We therefore expect that as uplink resolution increases that the performance converges to (7). It is interesting to note that an increase in TA resolution will not necessarily result in an increase in performance across the entire magnitude of possible errors.

It is also intuitively satisfying that less resolution results in less large and small errors. Consider two annuli, one wide, the other narrow. If the angle that is randomly selected is located near the actual angle of the UE location (i.e., $\hat{\theta} \approx \theta$) the width of the narrow annulus allows for comparatively little error introduced by picking the wrong distance $\hat{\rho}$. Thus we expect to see less small errors with lower resolution. Now consider the case where the angle opposite that of the actual UE (i.e., $\hat{\theta} \approx \theta + \pi$) is randomly selected. The narrow annulus allows for comparatively little compensation in error by choosing a small ρ . Thus we expect to see less large errors with lower resolution.

B. CeSAR Assisted Timing Advance Inference

We next draw the reader's attention to the theoretical CeSAR result presented alongside simulated results in Figure 7 where the simulated results are obtained using LTE compliant simulation parameters. We see close agreement between the data and the theory. Worse performance is predicted in theory, especially at lower values of circular error probable⁴. This is due to an underlying assumption of the theory which considers

⁴Circular Error Probable (CEP) is defined as the probability that a position estimate will fall within some radius of the true position.

an error of each realization to be the distance between position estimate and the terminus of the arc-locus (the arc-locus being described by the initial Weibull distributed angle). In reality, the UE will not necessarily be located at that extreme, but somewhere else along the arc-locus resulting in some smaller error.

With Figure 7 we can also predict expected performance gains. Across the spectrum of error magnitude the CeSAR theory predicts significant improvement. For instance, at CEP 70% over 200 meters of improvement in performance can be expected.

C. Minimum Location Information Inference Robustness

Recall Corollaries 2 and 3 which followed from Theorems 1 and 2 respectively. Corollary 2 introduced a natural weakness of location information inference from a timing advance only in that for UEs that maintain a constant distance from the eNB due to the scaled version of (12) showed significant negative skew. Corollary 3 contrasted this result by showing that when a UE maintained constant distance from the eNB, the distribution of error described by (15) when CeSAR is used has positive skew.

The findings of these corollaries are confirmed in simulation where the UE maintains the cell edge in a LTE compliant network. The results are presented in Figure 8. Both the cumulative density for the unassisted case and the CeSAR assisted case correspond to the shapes predicted by (12) and (15) respectively. The CeSAR assisted curve also shows that half of the estimate errors (i.e., CEP 50%) will be within 158 meters of the true location. This stands in opposition to the unassisted case with a CEP 50% of 671 meters, over half the distance of the cell itself.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have provided theoretical analysis of location information inference by timing advance and via the

CeSAR method. Our analysis was supported with simulated results which highlighted the weakness of inferring location via timing advance only and the benefit to assisting location inference via CeSAR. Through analysis we showed how an improvement of over 200 meters in accuracy (in terms of CEP 70%) could be expected by using CeSAR.

Second, through simulation and analysis, we showed how we can expect the theoretical performance to change as the timing advance resolution changes. A case study was presented in terms the distribution of errors in a GSM network compared with an LTE network. A significant result was location inference will not necessarily improve across the magnitude of possible errors as TA resolution increases. In other words, higher TA resolution may lower the number of smaller errors, yet still increase the number of larger errors.

Finally, the implications in terms of location information inference mitigation was discussed. To this end, it was demonstrated that location information inference would be particularly poor when a UE maintained constant distance from the eNB. This weakness was shown to be mitigated through CeSAR, providing over 500 meters improvement in accuracy when the UE maintains constant range from the eNB.

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